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THE ROLE OF HUMOR IN SUCCESSFUL MEME MARKETING CAMPAIGNS: THE CASE OF RYANAIR

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the importance and impact of meme culture and meme marketing, with a focus on the case of Ryanair Airlines. A meme can be defined as a visual or idea that is popular in internet culture and is often humorously portrayed. Meme culture has rapidly grown in the digital age with the widespread use of social media, and as such, meme culture and meme marketing have become effective tools that brands can use to connect with their target audience.

Ryanair has successfully implemented a marketing strategy using meme marketing. Specifically, the company's aggressive pricing strategy and humorous advertising campaigns, combined with the popularity of internet memes, have had a significant impact. In addition to offering customers cheap airfare, Ryanair has also attracted attention through its humorous advertisements. These ads have been shared on social media platforms and have gone viral.

The study uses a qualitative content analysis method to examine the reasons and consequences of Ryanair's success using meme marketing to reach its target audience in the digital age. The data is collected from Ryanair's Instagram posts. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of meme culture and meme marketing, filling a gap in the literature. It is hoped that this study can assist other brands in developing their digital marketing strategies and building a stronger connection with their target audience.

Keywords: Popular Culture, Meme Marketing, Ryanair, Internet Memes, Social Media

INTRODUCTION

Objectives of the Research

The study analyzes the importance and impact of meme culture and meme marketing, focusing on the case of Ryanair Airlines. Meme culture, which has grown rapidly in the digital age, is a popular tool for brands to connect with their target audience.

Ryanair has successfully used meme marketing to implement its marketing strategy, combining its aggressive pricing strategy and humorous advertising campaigns with the popularity of internet memes. The study aims to help other brands develop their digital marketing strategies and establish a stronger connection with their target audience.

Definition of Meme and Etymology

Reviewing the Literature In 1976, Richard Dawkins coined the term meme in his *The Selfish Gene* book for the first time [1]. It means an image, video, piece of text, etc., typically humorous in nature, that is copied and spread rapidly by internet users, often with slight variations [2].

He imagined the human culture as a soup. And that the replicator to be used for the transfer of the soup, needs a name, Richard Dawkins decided to call it meme. It is derived from a Greek root 'mimeme' and could also be thought of as being related to 'memory' [1].

It should be pronounced to rhyme with 'cream' according to Dawkins [1]. The term "meme" sounds similar to the Turkish word "mimik," which means facial expression. Because internet memes often use images with exaggerated or humorous facial expressions, the term "mim pazarlama" has been used in Turkish to describe marketing strategies that rely on internet memes.

Figure 1 and 2 : Example of Memes (Success Kid¹ and Roll Safe²)

Difference Between Viral Marketing and Meme Marketing

While viral content spread through sharing, meme content spread through imaginatively repurposing the original material. Existing research has studied the causes of these activities, and they are distinguishable [3]. Viral content is online content that achieves a high level of awareness due to shares and exposure on social media networks, news websites, aggregators, email newsletters and search engines [4].

Figure 3 : A Viral Marketing Example (Arnavut Şevket³, Çipetpet, Gençturkcell)
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Viral content in marketing is only usable for the short period of time when they become popular. They do not have any intention to convey a message or make people think, and there is no hidden message. They are used solely for the high visibility that viral content provides. As seen in Figure 3, Şevket Kopal, also known as Arnavut Şevket³, is an elderly individual who is interested in birdkeeping as a hobby in Istanbul [5]. He became viral in 2011 for his funny noises in a video where he claimed to understand the sounds made by goldfinch birds and their meanings. After the video, he started appearing in advertisements of well-known brands such as Turkcell and participating in TV shows³. However, due to the nature of viral content, his fame was short-lived. In the present day, not many people remember him.

Figure 4 and 5: Meme Contents Spreads with Slightly Different Variations. (Distracted Boyfriend⁴)

In contrast to viral content, memes spread through being reshared with small changes. These changes can include altering the written captions, removing or adding characters, or even completely revamping the scene. As a result, memes can survive for a long time and become known by larger audiences (even spanning countries and continents). The "Distracted Boyfriend" meme⁴, as seen in Figure 4, was a street photograph taken by Antonio Guillem, uploaded to a stock photo website in 2015. In years, people began sending the photo to each other with various messages by altering it, as seen in Figure 6. This meme, which remains one of the most well-known memes today, has demonstrated that memes can be more effective than viral content in marketing.

Figure 6: Variations of the Same Meme in Years. (Distracted Boyfriend⁴)

Ryanair Airlines' History and Success

Ryanair is an Irish low-cost airline that was founded in 1984 by Tony Ryan. It started operations with a single 15-seat plane, flying from Waterford to London [6]. Today, Ryanair has grown to become one of the largest airlines in Europe, operating more than 2,000 flights daily to over 200 destinations in 40 countries [7].

Ryanair's early years were marked by financial difficulties, with the airline struggling to compete with established carriers such as Aer Lingus and British Airways [6]. However, in 1991, Ryanair underwent a significant transformation, with the appointment of Michael O'Leary as CEO. Under his leadership, the company adopted a low-cost business model, focused on cutting costs and offering rock-bottom prices to customers.

Figure 7: Ryanair's total revenue graph in last 5 years

Ryanair's growth has been fueled in part by its aggressive expansion strategy, which has seen the company acquire a number of smaller airlines over the years. In 1998, Ryanair purchased the struggling Irish airline, Guinness Peat Aviation, which helped the company to establish a presence in Continental Europe [6]. In 2003, the airline acquired Buzz, a low-cost airline based in the UK, and in 2007, it purchased a 25% stake in Aer Lingus, its main rival. Today, Ryanair, Europe's leading ultra-low-cost airline. With over 1,800 daily flights, they are operate in 40 countries and serve 1500 routes, carrying over 150 million passengers each year [7].

Financial Reports of Ryanair and Correlations with Meme Marketing

As seen in figures 7 and 8, Ryanair's total revenue and net income have increased over the years. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and travel restrictions imposed worldwide in late 2019 and throughout 2021, the company's revenue has declined and profitability has turned

negative. Nevertheless, according to the latest financial report released in 2022, Ryanair has experienced a more successful commercial period than any previous year [7]. It is believed that the success is attributed to Ryanair's meme marketing strategy used on its Instagram account.

Net Profit-Ryanair's Financials (Million €)

Figure 8: Ryanair's net profit graph in last 5 years

METHODOLOGY

The study uses a qualitative content analysis method to examine the reasons and consequences of Ryanair's success using meme marketing to reach its target audience.

The data is collected from Ryanair's Instagram posts. The memes that were the subject of the research selected randomly from last months posts [8].

The study focuses on the memes used in Ryanair's Instagram posts and analyzes the memes' themes and messaging. The study also analyzes the reactions to Ryanair's Instagram posts and the impact they had on the airline's brand.

FINDINGS

Examinations of Ryanair's Instagram account reveals that they are gaining 1.111 followers weekly, resulting in a total of 33.330 followers monthly, as confirmed by the data (see Table 1).

Figure 9: Ryanair's Total Followers (Weekly)

Further examination of Ryanair's Instagram account shows that the airline posted an average of 44 media per week during the last month, resulting in a total of 120 media shared (see Table 1).

Figure 10: Ryanair's Total Media (Weekly)

Lastly, our examination of Ryanair's Instagram account reveals that during the last 2 weeks period, the airline shared a total of 47 posts, of which only 4 were not related to memes (see Table 1).

Figure 11: Meme Content (Yellow Area) is shared significantly more than Non-Meme Content (Blue Area).

Table 1: Instagram Stats of Ryanair Airlines

INSTAGRAM STATS SUMMARY FOR RYANAIR (2023-04-13 - 2023-04-27) (Resource: SocialBlade) [8]				
DATE	GAINED FOLLOWERS		NEW POSTS	
13.04.2023		953,715		4,031
14.04.2023	1.102	954,817	2	4,033
15.04.2023	752	955,569	1	4,034
16.04.2023	662	956,231	2	4,036

17.04.2023	696	956,927	3	4,039
18.04.2023	657	957,584	4	4,043
19.04.2023	905	958,489	4	4,047
20.04.2023	1.016	959,505	4	4,051
21.04.2023	1,217	960,722	4	4,055
23.04.2023	4,051	964,773	3	4,058
24.04.2023	3,102	967,875	4	4,062
25.04.2023	2,789	970,664	4	4,066
26.04.2023	2,673	973,337	5	4,071
27.04.2023	1,979	975,316	5	4,076
Daily Averages	1,111		4	
Last 30 days	33,33		120	

It also can be asserted that Ryanair is engaged in a distinct marketing approach from its competitors, as the utilization of meme marketing on its Instagram account is not observed among other low-cost airline companies in the industry.

For comparison, the Instagram pages of EasyJet and Wizz Air, which also provide low-cost airline services in Europe, were examined [9]. Neither of them were found to be using a meme marketing strategy like Ryanair's. Additionally, it was observed that the follower count of these rival companies is significantly lower when compared to Ryanair's follower count, which is almost 1 million.

Figure 12, 13 and 14: Some Memes Posted by Ryanair's Instagram Account
(Roll Safe ², Pingu ⁵, Louis Looking At Pill Bottle ⁶)

CONCLUSION

Theoretical Contributions

This study adds to the literature on meme marketing by examining the role of humor in successful campaigns. It highlights the importance of cultural relevance and contextual appropriateness of humorous content in enhancing engagement and brand recall. The study provides insights into the underlying mechanisms of humor in generating positive affect and attitudes towards the brand.

Managerial Contributions

The findings offer practical implications for marketers on how to leverage humor and memes to enhance brand awareness and engagement. The study suggests the need for consideration of the target audience's cultural background and appropriateness of humor in the campaign.

It highlights the benefits of incorporating user-generated content and audience participation in meme marketing campaigns to enhance authenticity and credibility. This study is a descriptive research of preliminary investigation related to meme marketing, which is a relatively new concept. It is observed that Ryanair has achieved increasing success in recent years and has also been using meme marketing intensively. Of course, with this research, we cannot directly prove the contribution of meme marketing to Ryanair's success, but it is worth researching the topic with correlational and causal research to be conducted in the future.

Future Research

Further studies can investigate the impact of different types of humor on brand attitudes and purchase intentions. Additionally, future research can explore the effectiveness of meme marketing campaigns in different industries and cultural contexts. Furthermore, more research is needed to understand the potential negative effects of humor in meme marketing, such as the

risk of offending or alienating certain segments of the audience. Finally, future research can investigate the impact of meme marketing on long-term brand loyalty and customer retention.

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